

SYNTHESIS and BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION of NOVEL BENZOTRIAZOLE DERIVATIVES as ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS

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ABSTRACT

Benzotriazole is a bicyclic heterocyclic structure with three atoms of nitrogen and a fused benzene ring. Benzotriazole exhibits a broad spectrum of pharmacological and biological functions. A broad range of biological activities, such as antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, anthelmintics, antiprotozoal, anti-inflammatory, anti mycobacterial, antihypertensive and analgesic effects, are exhibited by benzotriazole. The vast majority of medications are available to treat a wide range of illnesses, but they are not without drawbacks, such as toxicity, resistance, and various adverse effects. The creation of novel chemical entities with greater activity and increased efficacy is required to address these problems. The present study involves in synthesizing four novel benzotriazole derivatives and characterization of the synthesized derivatives by using Mass, IR and NMR spectras and evaluating the anti-bacterial activity of the prepared compounds.

Keywords : Benzotriazole, Benzotriazole derivatives, Mass spectra, IR spectra, NMR spectra, anti-bacterial activity.

INTRODUCTION

The fight against infectious illnesses has become an endless process since microorganisms are changing genetically at a faster rate than new medications are being developed, and they are also becoming resistant to many antibiotics and therapeutic compounds used to treat different diseases, The triazole class has garnered a lot of attention in recent decades because of its extensive application in agriculture as well as industry. The compound benzotriazole (figure 1) and its derivatives are highly significant in medical chemistry. The nitrogen- containing bicyclic ring system known as benzotriazole derivatives has been shown to exhibit a variety of biological actions, including antibacterial, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antimalarial, analgesic, and antitubercular activity[1]. Derivatives of benzotriazoles also have antiprotozoal as well as antihelminthic properties.

Fig . 1 Structure of benzotriazole

Three tautomers exist for benzotriazole : two 1H- forms and one 2H- form. The equilibrium in solution is nearly entirely located on the 1H- forms side [2]. Despite having a pKa of 8.2, benzotriazole is a stronger NH-acid than benzimidazole or 1,2,3-triazole , indazole, despite being a very weak base [3].

TABLE I
THE PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF BENZOTRIAZOLE

Molecular Formula	C ₆ H ₅ N ₃
Molecular Weight	119.1240
Density	1.36 g/cm ³
Melting point	98.5 to 100°C
Solubility in Water	g/100 ml is 2 (moderate)
Nature	White to brown crystalline powder
UV absorbance	286 nm
CAS Registry Number	95-14-7

In the manufacturing of rubber, chemical fiber and plastic, benzotriazoles are frequently utilized as photostabilizers, inhibitors of corrosion as well as radioprotectors [4]. In addition to these functions, benzotriazole is crucial as a precursor for the preparation of acid azides, peptides and 3-hydroxymethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzofurans [5].

The review of the literature shows that heterocyclic compounds with benzotriazoles as the primary molecule exhibited a wide range of biological actions, including antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, anticancer as well as anticonvulsant effects. The effectiveness of benzotriazole derivatives as antimicrobials has been demonstrated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All the materials and reagents were obtained from commercial sources such as Pine chem industry and thermo chemicals Lmt. Precoated TLC silica gel plates purchased from S.D.Fine were used to confirm the components purity and the reactions progression. EZ Melt automatic melting point equipment and an open capillary tube were used to assess the melting points of all the compounds. All the compounds that are synthesized were characterized by spectral analysis like Mass, FTIR spectra and ¹H NMR spectrometry. The final compounds were screened for their anti-bacterial activity.

Procedures

Synthesis of Benzotriazole

Orthophenylenediamine (10.8gm) was dissolved in a mixture of 12gms (11.5ml) of glacial acetic acid and 30ml of water content in 250ml beaker. The clear solution was cooled to 15°C and stirred then added a solution of (7.5gms) of NaNO₂ in 15ml of water in one portion and add 3 to 5 drops of ammonium hydroxide to the reaction mixture until violet colour appears on the pH paper and then filter the mixture and the obtained product is dried in hot air oven at 40°C for 3 hours.

Fig . 2 Scheme for the synthesis of benzotriazole

Synthesis of derivative A : 1-(pyridin-2-yl)-1H-1,2,3-benzotriazole

In a 250ml beaker 1.50gms Benzotriazole, 1.25gms pyridine are taken and dissolved in 12ml of methanol under ice cold water. The above mixture is taken in a flask, slowly add 1.02ml of formaldehyde to the mixture followed by heating using reflux at 40°C for 4 hours. The reaction progress can be monitored by TLC (Thin Layer Chromatography), after the reaction is complete allow the mixture to cool at room temperature and the content is taken in a beaker and kept in the freezer overnight. The product was crystallised using methanol and it is filtered and dried.

Synthesis of derivative B : 2-(Benzotriazol-1-yl) aniline

The amount of 1.50gms Benzotriazole, 1.20gms of aniline are taken in the beaker and dissolved in 12ml of methanol. The mixture is taken the flask and slowly add 1.02ml of formaldehyde followed by heating it using reflux at 40°C for 4 hours. Then

the reaction progress can be monitored by TLC, after the reaction is complete allow the mixture to cool at room temperature and the content is kept in the beaker overnight. The product was crystallised using the methanol and it is filtered and dried.

Synthesis of derivative C: 2-(Benzotriazol-1-yl) Para-Nitro Aniline

Dissolve 1.50gms of Benzotriazole in 12ml of methanol and add 1.30gms of Para nitro aniline and the mixture in the flask. Slowly add 1.02ml of formaldehyde followed by heating it using reflux at 40°C for 4 hours. Then the reaction progress can be monitored by TLC, after the reaction is complete allow the mixture to cool at room temperature and the content is kept in the beaker overnight. The product was crystallised using the methanol and it is filtered and dried.

Synthesis of derivative D : 1-(Benzotriazol-1-yl) - N,N- Dimethyl amine

In the 250ml flask add 1.50gms of Benzotriazole, 1.30gms of N,N Dimethyl amine are dissolved in 12ml of methanol. Slowly add 1.02ml of formaldehyde followed by heating it using reflux at 40°C for 4 hours. Then the reaction progress can be monitored by TLC, after the reaction is complete allow the mixture to cool at room temperature and the content is kept in the beaker overnight. The product was crystallised using the methanol and it is filtered and dried.

Fig . 3 Scheme for the synthesis of benzotriazole derivatives

Fig . 4 Structures of benzotriazole derivatives A, B, C and D

ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

All the synthesized benzotriazole derivatives were screened for their antibacterial activity. The invitro antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds were assessed against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli* by cup plate method on nutrient agar medium. The nutrient agar plate was inoculated with test organism, with a depth of 4-5mm and then allow it to solidify. Ensure that the layers of medium are uniform in thickness. Divide the nutrient agar plate into four (4) equal parts. Then with the help of sterile borer make four cavities, one in each portion. Fill the cavity with the test solution and slowly incubated the plates at 37°c for 24 hours. Accurately measure the diameter or areas of circular inhibition zones. The antibacterial activity was determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone in mm [6-13].

Bacteria: The different species of bacteria used to carry out the antibacterial activity tests are *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*. Antibiotic assay media, sterile discs are used

Culture media:

TABLE II
ANTIBIOTIC ASSAY MEDIA

Composition:	g/ lit
Peptone	6
Pancreatic digest of casein	4
Yeast extract	3
Beef extract	1.5
Dextrose	1
Agar	15

Final PH (After sterilization) 7.9 + 0.1

Generally the antibacterial activity of the compound is expressed in terms of its ability to inhibit the growth of bacteria in nutrient broth or agar. The bacterial growth inhibition can be measured by two methods.

They are:

1. Diffusion method and
2. Dilution method

Dilution method : This method is used to determine the minimal concentration of antibacterial to inhibit or kill the microorganism. This minimal concentration is called as Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC). This method is measured by two methods, one broth dilution method and agar dilution method

Diffusion method: This is of two types; one is paper disc diffusion method and agar diffusion method (or) cup plate method. This method followed here for testing the anti-bacterial Cup plate method.

Cup plate method: Media are made up of the final concentrations used in the usual methods of microbiological assay, but with addition of 1-5 per cent of agar. Eleven-ml, portions of medium are placed in Pyrex bacteriological test tubes, autoclaved at 10th, for 10 minutes and stored in the refrigerator until required. Just before use the tubes are heated in the boiling water- bath to melt the medium and then held in a bath at 45°C until needed. The tubes are now inoculated with 1ml of a suitable suspension of organism, after thorough mixing by several inversions, the medium is poured into Petri dishes, which are allowed to cool on a flat bench. It is essential to use dishes of which the circular inner surface is plane and level. Four holes are cut in the agar by means of a sharp 10-mm. Cork borer, the underside of the plates are marked to permit subsequent identification of the cups. Three drops of test or standard solutions are now added to the appropriate cups from a pipette of the type used in ampicillin estimations, in which the dropper has a platinum tube of 0.0365 inch external 0.0295 inch internal diameter and about 12mm, long, fused into the tip at an angle of about 130 degree to take up a position normal to the Petri dish during delivery. A pipette of this type has been found to give drops highly uniform in size. The plates are incubated at a temperature suitable for the organism used. The width of the zones of growth may be measured after 18 hours incubation, but it has been found that under the conditions so far investigated, the diameters are not altered by longer incubation. During preparation of the plates strict asepsis is unnecessary, normal cleanliness and the use of oven-dried apparatus have so far avoided all trouble from contaminating organisms and it has also been found unnecessary to sterilise either test or standard solutions.

Cup plate method:

Preparation of antibiotic culture media: The culture media was prepared according to the composition and the final was adjusted to PH 7.40+ 0.01 after sterilization.

Preparation of Petri plates: The prepared antibiotic culture media was poured into the Petri plates to get a depth of 4mm. About 25-30ml of antibiotic culture media was poured in Petri plates with diameter of 100mm.

Preparation of antibiotic stock solution: Antibiotic may be received as powder or tablets. Powder was weighed accurately dissolved in the appropriate diluents to yield the required concentrations using sterile glass ware. The standard drug Ampicillin powder of 10 mg was dissolved the 10 mL. Solvent to get a concentration of 1mg/ml. This was used as stock solution. From this different dilutions were prepared. The different concentrations prepared were 100 µg/ml, 500 µg/ml, 1000 µg/ml. Cup plate method: The anti bacterial activity was done by using the cup plate method.

TABLE III

ZONE OF INHIBITION OF THE DERIVATIVES

ZONE OF INHIBITION ZOI (mm)				
Compound	Species	Concentration (µg/ml)		
		100	500	1000
Compound 1 (Benzotriazole) Compound 1a (Derivative A) Compound 1b (Derivative B) Compound 1c (Derivative C) Compound 1d (Derivative D) Ampicillin	<i>Bacillus subtilus</i>	9 11 8 7.2 7.8 10	11 12 9 8.0 8.7 15	18 21 12 12 11.6 18
Compound 1 (Benzotriazole) Compound 1a (Derivative A) Compound 1b (Derivative B) Compound 1c (Derivative C) Compound 1d (Derivative D) Ampicillin	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6.0 7.2 5.1 6.0 7.0 7.5	7.0 8.5 7.5 7.2 7.7 8.0	8.5 9.0 8.5 8.3 8.0 10.0

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS**Results and discussion of synthesized compounds****1-(pyridin-2-yl)-1H-1,2,3-benzotriazole (compound 1)**

The percentage yield : 72 % , m.p . 155-157°C, the formation of compound was evident from the **IR** spectrum by the appearance of broad peak at the 1071.35 cm⁻¹, due to the presence of Carbon- Nitrogen compound [Fig ...], **¹H NMR** spectrum by the appearance of triplet at 7.9 ppm Protons present on C5,C7 carbons, triplet at 7.6 ppm protons on C5, C6 Carbons [Fig ...]. Mass spectrum [**ESI-MS**] by the appearance of molecular ion peak [**M**] at m/z [%] 198.0 [10] [Fig]

2-(Benzotriazol-1-yl) aniline (compound 2)

The percentage yield : 83 % , m.p . 182-185°C, the formation of compound was evident from the **IR** spectrum by the appearance of broad peak at the 740.18 cm⁻¹, this is due to the presence of Nitrogen-Hydrogen compound, **¹H NMR** spectrum by the appearance of triplet at 7.5 ppm Protons present on C5, C7 carbons , triplet at 7.0 ppm 2 protons on C5, C6 Carbons .Mass spectrum [**ESI-MS**] by the appearance of molecular ion peak [**M**] at m/z [%] 211.3.

2-(Benzotriazol-1-yl) Para-Nitro Aniline (compound 3)

The percentage yield : 85 % , m.p . 220-224°C, the formation of compound was evident from the **IR** spectrum by the appearance of broad peak at the 3339.15 cm⁻¹, this is due to presence of Nitrogen-Hydrogen compound, **¹H NMR** spectrum by the appearance of triplet at 7.4 ppm Protons present on C5 carbon, triplet at 7.6 ppm protons on C7 Carbon. Mass spectrum [**ESI-MS**] by the appearance of molecular ion peak [**M**] at m/z 256.2.

1-(Benzotriazol-1-yl) - N,N- Dimethyl amine (compound 4)

The percentage yield : 88 % , m.p . 157-159.45°C, the formation of compound was evident from the **IR** spectrum by the appearance of broad peak at the 737.49 this is due to the presence of Nitrogen-Hydrogen compound , **¹H NMR** spectrum by the appearance of triplet at 7.4 ppm Protons present on C6 carbon, triplet at 7.6 ppm protons on C7 Carbons. Mass spectrum [**ESI-MS**] by the appearance of molecular ion peak [**M**] at m/z [%] 164.2.

Results and discussion of Antibacterial activity:

The compound 1a at 100 µg/ml conc. Showed good activity compared to 1b,1c and 1d where the ZOI is (11mm) in *B.subtilis*. The ZOI of 1b,1c,1d was found to be (8mm,7.2mm and 7.8mm).

The compound 1a at 500 µg/ml conc. Showed good activity compared to 1b,1c and 1d where the ZOI is (12mm) in *B. subtilis*. The ZOI of 1b,1c,1d was found to be (9mm,8.0mm and 8.7mm).

The compound 1a at 1000 µg/ml conc. Showed good activity compared to 1b,1c and 1d where the ZOI is (21mm) in *B.subtilis*. The ZOI of 1b,1c,1d was found to be (12mm,12mm and 11.6mm).

The compound 1a at 100 µg/ml conc. Showed good activity compared to 1b,1c and 1d where the ZOI is (7.2mm) in *E.coli*. The ZOI of 1b,1c,1d was found to be (5.1mm,6.0mm and 7.0mm).

The compound 1a at 500 µg/ml conc. Showed good activity compared to 1b,1c and 1d where the ZOI is (8.5mm) in *E.coli*. The ZOI of 1b,1c,1d was found to be (7.5mm,7.2mm and 7.7mm).

The compound 1a at 1000 µg/ml conc. Showed good activity compared to 1b,1c and 1d where the ZOI is (9mm) in *E.coli*. The ZOI of 1b,1c,1d was found to be (8.5mm,8.3mm and 8.0mm).

The compound 1a was showing good anti-bacterial activity than compound 1b,1c and 1d in *B.subtilis* species and *E.coli* species.

CONCLUSION

The proposed compound benzotriazole and its derivatives were synthesized and the derivatives are characterized by the spectral data (IR, NMR AND MASS) and further evaluated for antibacterial activity. Even though all the synthesized benzotriazole derivatives showed remarkable ZOI (Zone of inhibition) with standards and have good antibacterial activities, the compound 1a was showing good anti-bacterial activity than compound 1b,1c and 1d in *B.subtilis* species and *E.coli* species.

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